

HPC-JEEP: Energy-based charging on the ARCHER2 HPC service

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1. Introduction

National supercomputing and HPC services such as [ARCHER2](#) and [DiRAC](#) represent large investments in DRI by UKRI to serve UK research and use large amounts of electricity (for example, ARCHER2 can draw ~4 MW at peak load). Traditionally, resources on such services have been granted in units of compute time (core-hours, node-hours, etc.) with users not informed, nor paying much attention to their energy use; and services not generally reporting breakdowns of energy use other than for total electricity charges. Without an understanding of how research areas, projects and users use energy and how efficiently they use resources it is difficult to plan future procurements or service strategies towards a net zero goal. The HPC-JEEP project is looking at what level of energy information can be extracted from current and historical per-job data from ARCHER2 and DiRAC services; and how this data can be analysed and synthesised to provide the information required for funders (who procure and set service strategy and objectives) and researchers (who make decisions about how best to use the resources they are granted) to allow them to make informed decisions about how to manage HPC resources to extract the maximum research benefit in the most emissions efficient way. The challenges the project is trying to address are:

1. What evidence can we provide from current HPC energy usage data to support users and funders towards net zero?
2. What could be the potential impacts of moving to job charging based on energy/emissions use to support net zero goals based on current evidence?
3. What are the best energy/emissions metrics that could be provided to HPC users and funders to help them support net zero goals?

In this report we address primarily Challenge 2: *What could be the potential impacts of moving to job charging based on energy/emissions use to support net zero goals based on current evidence?*. In particular, we have taken data that can currently be extracted from the ARCHER2 national HPC service and recalculated the charging based on different possible energy unit based approaches and examined the impact on different user communities.

The report is laid out in the following way: Section 2 provides a brief overview of the ARCHER2 system and a breakdown of power draw by different hardware components, Section 3 describes the methodologies used to extract and annotate the energy use data; Section 4 discusses the proposed approach to energy based charging; Section 5 presents the analysis of the different

charging scenarios and their impact on changes for use by different research areas and software; Section 6 provides some conclusions from the work so far and thoughts on implications of the rest of the project. The whole paper is supported by a dataset containing the raw data that was used for the analysis and the scripts and tooling that performed the analysis itself¹.

2. Hardware Details

ARCHER2

ARCHER2 is the UK national supercomputing service funded by UKRI (via EPSRC and NERC) with the HPC platform provided by HPE and the hosting and support provided by EPCC at The University of Edinburgh. The ARCHER2 system is a liquid-cooled HPE Cray EX with 5,860 compute nodes giving a total of 750,080 compute cores. ARCHER2 is one of the largest HPC systems without GPU accelerators in the world and sits at #28 in the November 2022 Top500 list of supercomputers². As well as the hardware platform, the ARCHER2 service provides a range of support for users and beyond, including a team of expert RSEs at EPCC to provide support for the research community, an extensive training programme and an outreach component. ARCHER2 is a general-purpose service supporting a wide range of research communities and software with a corresponding wide range of technical requirements and use cases.

Compute nodes

The ARCHER2 compute nodes are CPU only (*i.e.* they do not have any GPU accelerators available) with a total of 128 physical CPU cores per node. There are 5860 compute nodes, each with:

- 2x AMD EPYC™ 7742 64c 2.25GHz processors
- 256/512 GB DDR4 memory
- 2x 100 Gbps Slingshot 10 interconnect interfaces (one per processor)

Interconnect

- HPE Cray Slingshot 10 - ethernet based, dynamic routing
- Dragonfly topology - maximum of 3 hops between any two compute nodes
- 768 switches in the whole system

Storage

- 3x ClusterStor L300 Lustre file systems, each 3.6 PB
- 1 PB ClusterStor E1000F solid state storage
- 4x NetApp FAS8200A file systems, 1 PB total

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7701495>

² <https://www.top500.org/lists/top500/list/2022/11/>

Power profile

Based on data from HPE, we have the following estimates of power draw for components:

- Slingshot interconnect switches: approx. 700 W per switch, 768 switches in the system, 540 kW in total
- ClusterStor Lustre file systems: approx. 8 kW per file system, 5 file systems in system, 40 kW in total
- Cooling Distribution Units (CDU): 16 kW per CDU, 6 CDU in the system, 96 kW in total

Given that each compute node has an estimated maximum power draw of around 600 W and there are 5860 compute nodes, this gives a total maximum power draw for the compute nodes of around 3,500 kW. This, in turn, gives an estimated maximum power draw for the ARCHER2 system of over 4,000 kW with the following rough percentage breakdown by component:

- Compute nodes: 83%
- Slingshot interconnect switches: 14%
- CDU: 2%
- ClusterStor Lustre file systems: 1%

This breakdown indicates that the compute node energy use is by far the most significant component of energy use for jobs on the ARCHER2 system. For large jobs there may be some contribution from interconnect use, but file system energy use is a negligible component for all jobs.

One observation from ARCHER2 is that the compute node idle power draw is a large fraction of the peak power draw. An idle compute node on ARCHER2 typically draws 200-250 W (around 40% of the peak power draw). The processors typically draw around 40 W on an idle node and the memory around 115 W. We assume that the remaining idle power draw (around 100 W) is mostly due to the Slingshot interconnect cards. On ARCHER2, this does not lead to issues with excess energy use as the utilisation is so high (over 90%) but, if the system was less busy, this would lead to a large power draw even if the system was not being used. The ARCHER2 service is working with HPE to understand how this high idle compute node power draw can be reduced.

This energy consumption is in-system only, and thus does not include inefficiencies due to the plant backing the hardware; e.g. UPS (ARCHER2 compute nodes are not on UPS, they are on raw electricity feeds) and external cooling infrastructure.

ARCHER2 energy is provided by a certified 100% renewable energy contract.

3. Methodology

ARCHER2

On ARCHER2, the node energy data is taken from the HPE Cray Power Management counters provided by the HPE Cray Baseboard Management Controller (BMC). The Slurm “pm_counters” energy plugin³ combines the data from all compute nodes involved in each job to produce an overall node energy use for the job which is stored in the Slurm accounting database in the “ConsumedEnergyRaw” and “ConsumedEnergy” fields. The node energy use covers all components in the compute node, including processors, memory, interconnect cards and other parts.

The energy usage by system components external to compute nodes is not currently included or accounted for in the energy use data. Items not accounted for include the interconnect switches, file systems and other parts external to the compute nodes (e.g. cooling infrastructure). The energy use by these components per-job will be substantially less than the energy use for the compute nodes themselves as indicated by the power profile information for ARCHER2 included in Section 2 above.

We obtain the per-job node energy use data (along with the other required job information) from Slurm by querying the accounting database directly and then use a Python program to analyse the data. The research area categorisation is taken from the per-project information contained in the EPCC SAFE database. The analysis scripts and a description of how they are used are available as part of the open dataset released along with this report⁴. The data fields that are taken from the ARCHER2 Slurm accounting database are:

- *JobIDRaw* - The unique job step ID
- *JobName* - The job step name - for Slurm job steps launched using srun (all parallel job steps on ARCHER2) this contains the executable name
- *Account* - On ARCHER2 this corresponds to the project budget code
- *NNodes* - Number of compute nodes used by the job step
- *NTasks* - Number of parallel processes launched for the job step
- *ElapsedRaw* - The job step runtime in seconds
- *State* - The final state of the job step (indicates if the job step completed successfully or not)
- *ConsumedEnergyRaw* - The total node energy used by the job step in joules
- *MaxRSS* - Maximum memory use - not used in this analysis
- *AvgRSS* - Mean memory use - not used in this analysis
- *ReqCPUFreq* - The requested CPU frequency - not used in this analysis

³ https://github.com/SchedMD/slurm/tree/master/src/plugins/acct_gather_energy/pm_counters

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7701495>

When read by the Python analysis script, these fields are stored in a Pandas dataframe and some additional fields are generated:

- *Energy* - Converts ConsumedEnergyRaw to kWh and marks those job steps that are missing energy data
- *NodePower* - Computes mean compute node power draw in Watts from the Energy and ElapsedRaw fields
- *CPN* (Cores per Node) - Calculates the number of cores used per compute node
- *Cores* - Total cores used
- *Software* - Software package used for the job step - derived from the executable name in JobName matched against a regex library of known applications
- *Motif* - Computational motifs associated with the job step - derived from the identified software package
- *Area* - The research area associated with the job step - derived from the project code in the Account field and the mapping from project code to research area taken from EPCC SAFE

Finally, the analysis script recomputes charging according to the specified charging scenario (see description of scenarios below) and compares this to the current charging approach. The output from this script forms that basis of the analysis presented below.

4. Allocation units and charging approaches

Allocation units

There are two parts to allocations and charging on HPC systems that allocate consumable budgets to projects/users:

1. How the unit of allocation is defined - what properties on the system are used to calculate the consumable budget and the amount of budget decremented when the system is used by a project/user
2. What monetary cost is assigned to the units of allocation

This report is concerned with point 1 - the definition of the unit of allocation. We will discuss how these allocation units relate to monetary cost but will not define the monetary cost of allocation units for ARCHER2.

It should also be noted that not all HPC systems allocate resources to projects/users using a consumable budget. Some services use a fair share approach and define a share of the system to projects/users. Discussions about the allocation unit should be transferable to systems that use a fair share approach (with shares defined using different allocation units) but we have not investigated this in any detail as neither of the HPC systems used in the HPC-JEEP project have a fair share system as their primary method of resource allocation.

Energy-based allocation unit models

The general formula for the calculation of the charge for a job based on the models in this report is

$$C_T = wC_E + (1 - w)C_R$$

In this formula:

- w is the weight: a value in the interval $[0,1]$ that defines the relative weight of charging for energy use of the job to the residency of the job
- C_E is the computed charge for the energy use of the job - proportional to the energy use (e.g in kWh, J)
- C_R is the computed charge for the residency of the job - proportional to the residency (e.g. in node-h, coreh-h, GPU-h)

ARCHER2 currently uses this formula with $w = 0$ so that the charge for jobs is just based on the residency with no component of energy. The weighting should capture what proportion of the total cost of the system lies in the capital cost and what proportion of the cost lies in the energy costs. Of course, at the start of the service, this will be an estimate as you will not know, *a priori*, how much your energy costs are going to be over the lifetime of the service. For example, for

ARCHER2, an estimate may be that the energy cost of the system will be equivalent to a third of the capital cost and so you could use $w = 0.25$.

C_R is computed as:

$$C_R = R/S_R$$

Where R is the residency in a unit such as node-h, core-h or GPU-h and the S_R is a scaling factor. On ARCHER2 the residency, R , is measured in node-h and S_R is 1, so C_R is in units of raw node-h.

C_E is computed as:

$$C_E = E/S_E$$

Where E is the energy in a unit such as kWh or J and S_E is a scaling unit of energy per unit of residency. On ARCHER2, for example, the unit of residency is node-h and the unit of energy is kWh so S_E is in kWh/node-h or, kW/node - the average node power draw.

The value of S_E is essentially a prediction of what the correct average per-node power draw is to give an overall energy use that matches as closely as possible to what the actual measured used energy will be over the future allocation period (remember, we want our charging model to match onto actual monetary costs of the service). As we will use the per-job energy as reported by Slurm to compute the charging, we will look at the historical values that this measurement gives for the per-node power draw to provide a guide for the value of S_E .

Table 1, below, compares the weighted median of per-job mean node power draws (weighted by use) computed from per-job energy data from Slurm on ARCHER2 for three months: July, August and September 2022. We have picked these three months as prior to July 2022 there was a bug in compute node energy measurement on ARCHER2 and in October 2022 the ARCHER2 system was reduced in size temporarily for maintenance work on the cooling system. Both of these would have had an impact on the average node power draw.

Table 1: Weighted median of per-job mean node power draws (weighted by use) for the three months in the period analysed

<i>Month</i>	<i>Weighted median per-node power draw</i>
Jul 2022	0.490 kW/node
Aug 2022	0.477 kW/node
Sep 2022	0.479 kW/node

Based on this data, 0.480 kW/node would be a reasonable choice for the value of S_E if these periods are considered to be representative of the service energy use going forward.

In mid-December 2022 the default CPU frequency for parallel jobs on ARCHER2 compute nodes was changed from 2.25 GHz to 2.0 GHz to improve energy efficiency⁵. If effective, this change should reduce the per-node median power draw significantly. Using the same analysis as used for the table above, the weighted median node power draw for the month period 14 Dec 2022 - 13 Jan 2023 is: 0.352 kW/node. We will continue to use the higher number in our analysis of the three month period where the CPU frequency was higher for consistency reasons but any real implementation of energy-based charging on ARCHER2 will need to take into account the changes from the reduction in default CPU frequency on the system.

⁵ <https://www.archer2.ac.uk/news/2022/12/12/CPUFreq.html>

5. Results

In this section we take the jobs from three monthly periods on ARCHER2 (Jul 2022, Aug 2022, Sep 2022) and recompute the charges under various different energy-based charging scenarios. We then compare how the charge differs from the original, residency-based charging where jobs are charged based solely on how many node hours they consume. The scenarios we consider are:

1. Pure energy-based charging (no residency component) - i.e. $w = 1.0$
2. Assuming energy costs over the service lifetime are the same as capital costs - i.e. $w = 0.5$
3. Assuming energy costs over the service lifetime are a third of the capital costs - i.e. $w = 0.25$

In all three scenarios we use the $S_E = 0.48$ kW/node as a prediction of average per-node power draw from the analysis above and the standard residency unit, $S_R = 1$ nodeh. As noted above, following a recent change on ARCHER2, we expect this value to be lower by around 0.1 kW/node for ARCHER2 in the future. The analysis below is on data collected when ARCHER2 had the higher power draw profile so we use the higher value for the per-node power draw to illustrate the differences from residency-based charging alone.

Overall data

Table 2 summarises the change from residency-based charging of the different charging scenarios.

Table 2: Summary of change in charging levels compared to current, residency-based, approach to different energy-based charging scenarios.

Scenario	w	S_E	% change in charge from current charging			
			Jul 2022	Aug 2022	Sep 2022	Full Period
#1	1.0	0.48 kW/node	-10.3%	-8.3%	-10.9%	-9.9%
#2	0.5	0.48 kW/node	-5.1%	-4.2%	-5.5%	-4.9%
#3	0.25	0.48 kW/node	-2.6%	-2.1%	-2.7%	-2.5%

Introducing a component of energy-based charging to the calculation for ARCHER2 has the overall effect of reducing the charge during the periods in question when compared to a pure residency-based approach. Scenario #1 represents charging based purely on energy with no residency (i.e. capital cost) component and, as such, shows the largest variation. Based on estimates at the start of the ARCHER2 service, scenario #3 is the closest to the projected cost profile over the lifetime of the service based on estimates before the service started - though rising energy costs at time of writing may move the situation closer to scenario #2.

We now move on to look in more detail how a change to the charging scheme affects the charges for different research areas and software on ARCHER2 over the periods.

Broken down by research area

Figures 1 and 2 show the change in charge from the current ARCHER2 charging system for different research areas when a component of energy charging is introduced according to scenario #3. Most research areas see a modest change in the charge (+/- 5%) and many research areas see a reduction in the charge. These effects are both reasonable given the modest overall reduction in charge of 2.5% described above.

Points of interest are:

- Two areas see an increase in charge: biomolecular modelling (0.4%) and soft matter physics (1.9%)
- Three areas see a larger decrease in charge (more than 5%): climate science (-5.1%), optical physics (-11.2%) and geophysics and seismology (-7.4%)

The areas that have increased their charge use the following software:

- Biomolecular modelling: GROMACS (92%)
- Soft matter physics: LAMMPS (100%)

The areas that have seen a large decreases use the following software:

- Climate science: Met Office UM (76%)
- Optical physics: R-matrix codes (98%)
- Geophysics and seismology: CP2K (37%), LAMMPS (17%), Cluster (16%), VASP (15%)

To give us a different perspective of the effect of a change of charging approach, we have broken down the charging change by software.

Figure 1: Percent change in charge for research areas with more than 0.5% usage compared to current residency charge by introducing a component of energy charging on ARCHER2. Bars represent mean % change over the three charging periods (Jul, Aug, Sep 2022) and lines the variation across the three periods.

Figure 2: Percent change in charge with more than 0.5% usage compared to current residency charge by introducing a component of energy charging on ARCHER2. Bars represent % change over the three charging periods (Jul, Aug, Sep 2022).

Broken down by software

Figures 3 and 4 show the charging change broken down by software that has more than 0.2% of use (by nodeh) over the analysis period.

Most software that show a change larger than +/- 5% are those implicated in the research area analysis above:

- Met Office Unified Model (UM) - this software accounts for 76% of the use of Climate Science research area and its low energy density is primarily responsible for the reduction in charge for that research area.
- R-matrix - this software accounts for 98% of use in the Optical Physics research area and its low energy density is primarily responsible for the reduction in charge for that research area. This low energy density is due to the applications only using a subset of the cores available on a compute node.
- Cluster - this is a post-processing analysis software that does not use all the cores on a compute node. It is partly responsible for the lowering of the energy use of the Geophysics and Seismology research area.

Two pieces of software have larger (> 5%) reductions in charge are CRYSTAL and GS2 - the areas that these pieces of software are associated with (Materials Science and Plasma Physics respectively) do not show large changes in charge as energy-based charging is introduced. As these software packages do not constitute a large amount of use associated with the particular research area, they do not have a large influence on the charge change for any particular research area.

The LAMMPS software shows an overall reduction in charge despite being strongly associated with the Soft Matter Physics research area that increased its charge overall - this indicates that there are likely differences in how different research areas use the same software package so analysis by just research area or just software use are not always sufficient to distinguish energy use trends on HPC systems. To give some idea of this type of analysis, we plot the mean node power draw distribution for the different software in Figure 5. The mean node power draw is calculated by dividing the amount of energy used by the runtime of the job. Figure 5 shows that, although the mean node power draw of LAMMPS jobs is generally high compared to other software (which ties in with the increase in charge for the Soft Matter Physics research area), there is a substantial number of jobs that have a lower mean node power draw leading to an overall decrease in charge for LAMMPS jobs across the period when energy charging is introduced.

We are planning future work to analyse the data and gain insights into what gives rise to the differences in power draw across different software.

Figure 3: Percent change in charge for software packages with more than 0.2% use compared to current residency charge by introducing a component of energy charging on ARCHER2. Bars represent mean % change over the three charging periods (Jul, Aug, Sep 2022) and lines, the variation across the three periods.

Figure 4: Percent change in charge for software packages with more than 0.2% use compared to current residency charge by introducing a component of energy charging on ARCHER2. Bars represent % change over the three charging periods (Jul, Aug, Sep 2022).

Figure 5: Mean node power distribution weighted by usage in nodeh broken down by software. Width of the violins represents weighted frequency with indicated mean node power draw.

6. Conclusions and next steps

An allocation/charging model based on a combination of residency and energy use can be used for allocations/charging on ARCHER2 and would be able to reflect the distribution of cost of the system in a reasonable way. The approach used here gives us the flexibility to vary the fraction of residency/energy charging to best match the characteristics of the system and also allows for different choices for different use cases if a similar approach was taken on other HPC services. The model could also be expanded to encompass heterogeneous HPC systems with different architecture types or even to develop common, cost-based charging units with a components of energy cost that could be applied coherently across different HPC services.

If we chose an energy unit based on historical median node power draw then most research areas/applications do not vary in a significant way (they are within +/-5% of the current charges). This would make the transition to a new charging model straightforward for most user groups and means major changes to allocations are not generally required. Although this may seem that it means that there is little change in the allocation model compared to the present system, the introduction of an energy component to the charge potentially allows for the introduction of different initiatives around energy efficient use of HPC systems (e.g., energy-aware scheduling decisions) and also prepares the way for future services when the energy component of charging would be larger.

Only the Optical Physics and Geophysics and Seismology research areas show significant (> 5%) changes in the amount of resource charged. This is primarily due to their applications having large memory footprints leading to them using only half of the compute cores on a node (or even less). This demonstrates that the major difference in energy use comes from how many compute cores are actively used by applications. Further consideration of how to identify and set allocations for research projects which heavily underuse computational resources is required before moving energy-based charging into operation.

The next steps for this aspect of the work

- We need to agree a timetable for the introduction of energy-based charging on ARCHER2 with the service stakeholders. This includes engagement with the research councils - who set the overall project allocations on ARCHER2 - to decide how to update current project allocations ahead of the introduction of energy-based charging.
- The output from jobs on ARCHER2 will need to be modified to tell users how much energy their job used and what the charge would be under the proposed new charging scheme to start to give users a sense of how charging will change. The final technical report from the HPC-JEEP project will cover reporting of energy use metrics to users.
- The scaling factor (S_E) of the energy unit needs to be revisited in light of the change in the default CPU frequency on ARCHER2 from 2.25 GHz to 2.0 GHz as this will have had a large impact on average node power draw.

The approach taken here also provides a potential mechanism for emissions-based charging schemes. As for cost-based charging, we would envisage the charge split into two components:

a residency-based component that represents the embodied emissions from production, shipping and disposal of the system and a dynamic component that represents emissions from the energy required to run the actual job. There are additional complications arising for an emissions-based approach however, for example, the carbon density associated with energy generation will vary over time leading to varying charges for identical jobs depending on when they are run. This complication also provides a potential opportunity for users and HPC services to selectively schedule different types of workload for different carbon density regimes - aiming to maximise the impact of HPC services per unit of emissions. Further investigation would be needed into this to understand better the feasibility and practical aspects of introducing such a scheme.